

Comparative Study of Self- Concept and Sports Competition Anxiety Between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers

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Abstract

*The purpose of the study was “Comparative Study of self- concept and sports competition anxiety between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers”. The subjects for this study were male National Football players. One hundred forty four subjects were selected for the study. Seventy two were those High Achieving National Level Footballers and Seventy two were those Low Achieving National Level Footballers. The age group of footballers was ranged between 19 to 28 years. To find out the self- concept, sports competition anxiety of different National level football players, the research scholar selected the questionnaires namely self- concept, sports competition anxiety Questionnaire. To determine the comparative differentials of self- concept, sports competition anxiety between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers, the test of significance (*t*-Ratio) was employed. Further, the level of significance was set at 0.05 level of confidence. The findings of the study reveal that there was significant difference in case of self- concept where High Achieving National Level Footballers exhibited better self- concept in comparison with the Low Achieving National Level Footballers. The insignificant difference was found in case of sports competition anxiety test between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers may be due to the reason that the players were almost of the same standard with a similar kind of experience which must have been a probable cause.*

Keyword: *self- concept and sports competition anxiety.*

Introduction

Sports are as old as the human society and it holds a prominent place in the modern life. Millions of people participate in sports activities, watch and read about them and spend billions of dollars annually on sports

activities and equipment. It now enjoys a popularity which outstrips any other form of social activity. It has become an integral part of the educational process as physical education and sports have been included in the regular curriculum. The students are taught various games and sports in a systematic manner. Besides teaching, the students are evaluated in their performance. Many people participate in games and sports for deriving physical, mental, social and emotional benefits. self concept as “An organized configuration of perception of the self which are admissible to awareness. It is compared of such elements as the perception of one’s characteristics and abilities, the percept and concept of the self in relation to others and to the environment”. The mental and conceptual awareness one holds of himself. Includes: physical, psychological, and social attributes; and can be influenced by its attitudes, habits, beliefs and ideas. These components and attributes can each be condensed to the general concepts of self-image and the self-esteem. It is the state of mind in which the individual responds with discomfort to some event that has occurred or is going to occur. The person’s worries about the event, their occurrence and consequences in general are the sources of anxiety; however the anxiety can be either somatic or cognitive in nature. The unpleasant emotional state consisting of psycho-physiological responses to anticipation of unreal or imagined danger, ostensibly resulting from unrecognized intra-psychic conflict. Physiological concomitants include increased heart rate, altered respiration rate, sweating, trembling, weakness and fatigue; psychological concomitants include feelings of impending danger, apprehension and tension. Anxiety is a state of emotional and physical disturbances included in a person by real or imagined threat. In psychology the term refers to disturbances caused by threats that are only apparent to the individual and cause him to behave in a way that is not relevant to the true situations. It is the state of mind in which the individual responds with discomfort to some event that has occurred or is going to occur. The person’s worries about the event, their occurrence and consequences in general are the sources of anxiety; however the anxiety can be either somatic or cognitive in nature.

Objectives

- ❖ To explore the self-concept and sports competition anxiety of High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.
- ❖ To compare the self-concept of High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.
- ❖ To compare the anxiety of High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

The results of the study and the quantum of knowledge in physical education especially in the area of sports psychology and football.

Hypothesis It was hypothesized that there may not be any significant difference in self-concept, Sports Competition anxiety, between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

Methodology The study was confined to One hundred forty four Senior Level Footballers .Seventy two High Achieving and Seventy two Low Achieving National Level Footballers were selected (age group of 19 to 28 years). The data was collected in the 68th Shantosh Trophy National Football Tournament held Kanchanjangha Stadium Siliguri from 24th February to 9th March 2014. One hundred forty four subjects by administering the tests for the selected test items on the different National level football players.

Sampling The subjects for this study were male National Football players, One hundred forty four subjects were selected for the study. Seventy two were those High Achieving National Level Footballers and Seventy two were those Low Achieving National Level Footballers. The age group of footballers was ranged between 19 to 28 years.

Procedures

The self-concept score of the subjects was obtained by using Self-Concept Questionnaire (SCQ) developed by Dr. Raj Kumar Saraswat. The sports competition anxiety score of the subjects was obtained by using Sports Competition Anxiety Questionnaire developed by Renier-Martin.

Statistical Procedure

To determine the comparative differentials of Self-Concept and The sports competition anxiety between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers, the test of significance ('t'-Ratio) was employed. Further, the level of significance was set at 0.05 level of confidence.

Results

Table – 1

Significance Of Difference Between High Achieving And Low Achieving National Level Footballers On Self Concept In Numbers

Variables	M-1	M-2	MD	SE	't' Ratio	Required 't' Ratio
Self-Concept	186,00	180.18	05.82	01.65	03.52*	01.98

**** Significant at 0.05 level of Confidence***

M1 = Mean of High Achieving National Level Footballers

M2 = Mean of Low Achieving National Level Footballers

From the above table 1, it is revealed that there was significant difference in case of Self Concept Test as calculated 't' value (03.52) was greater than tabulated 't' value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significance with 142 degree of freedom. Thus, it may be concluded that there was significant difference between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers related to Self Concept Test, in

which mean Self Concept Test is significantly higher for High Achieving National Level Footballers than Low Achieving National Level Footballers at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the table 1 are presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Graphical Depiction of Mean values of Self Concept test between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

Table – 2

Significance Of Difference Between High Achieving And Low Achieving National Level Footballers On Sports Competition Anxiety In Numbers

Variables	M-1	M-2	MD	SE	't' Ratio	Required 't' Ratio
Sports Competition Anxiety	20.46	19.84	00.62	00.56	01.10	01.98

*** Significant at 0.05 level of Confidence**

M1 = Mean of High Achieving National Level Footballers

M2 = Mean of Low Achieving National Level Footballers

From the above table 2, it is revealed that there was insignificant difference in case of Sports Competition Anxiety Test as calculated 't' value (01.10) was less than tabulated 't' value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significance with 142 degree of freedom. Thus, it may be concluded that there was insignificant difference between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers related to Sports Competition Anxiety Test, in which mean Sports Competition Anxiety Test is insignificantly higher for High Achieving National Level Footballers than Low

Achieving National Level Footballers at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the table 2 are presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Graphical Depiction of Mean values of Sports Competition Anxiety test between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

Discussion

Significant difference was found in case of self-concept where High Achieving National Level Footballers exhibited better self-concept in comparison with the Low Achieving National Level Footballers. It may be due to the greater awareness of High Achieving National Level Footballers towards physical, social, temperamental, educational, moral and intellectual ability. The insignificant difference in sports competition anxiety test between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers may be due to the reason that the players were almost of the same standard with a similar kind of experience which must have been a probable cause. In addition, players have been coached by specialist coaches who must have played a significant role by imparting psychological aspects in the coaching which might have been a contributing factor in not finding out the significant difference. In addition, the High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers get a similar kind of exposure which also must be a contributing factor in the insignificant difference.

Conclusions

Within the limitations of the study and on the basis of the results of the study, the following conclusions may be drawn:

There was Significant difference was found in case of self-concept where High Achieving National Level Footballers exhibited better self-concept and in

comparison with the Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

The insignificant difference was found in case of sports competition anxiety where High Achieving National Level Footballers exhibited less anxiety in comparison with the Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

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